

Elimination The HIV From The Human Body Using Acoustics Nano-Waves

Research Article

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Abstract

In this paper i suggest a new method to eliminate the HI Virus from the human body , by acoustics nano-waves and send it through the human body . My idea is that the patient must be lying naked on a table and the surface of table contains acoustic nano-waves generators and between the table and the patient we need to put coupling gel ; which is medium that helps the waves to move from the first medium (generators) to a second medium (human body) and as reminder it works the same as the (ultrasound) but with a very high frequency when generate the waves it propagate in the whole human body and every time the waves meet with the HI Virus it breakthrough and destroy it[6]. Our work is interested in the elimination of this disease.

Keywords: Acoustics Nano-Waves; HIV; Eliminate the HI Virus.

Introduction

Tens of millions of people have been infected by the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) since it was first recognized in the early 1980s, and more than 20 million have died from ensuing disease [1].

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) is the virus that causes Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS). Infection with HIV can weaken the immune system in human body to a level at which it has difficulty fighting off certain infections [2].

The membrane of the virus HIV consists of glycoproteins (Gp120 –Gp41) which give to the virus its full function, Structure and function of an HIV gp120 and gp41 is well explained in [3-5]. and ravage the glycoproteins (Gp120 –Gp41) on the HIV's membrane using acoustic nono-waves well explained in [6].

The development of nanotechnology in the field of medicine can save a lot of human lives . this work is basicly based on applying nanotechnology (acoustics nano-waves) in the field of medicine and exactly the aids in which i propose a device that generates acoustics nano-waves with a high frequency that reaches to 2 THz .We are not interested in the frequency of the waves in the human body but also the great importance is generating these waves

where we need about 0,5 Thz to 2Thz and there is no effect no harm to the human body by this nano-waves.

Proposing The Device

The device is a table it's whole surface contains acoustic nano-waves generating cells (figure1). The waves frequency is between 0.5 and 2 THz to get the waves length between 2 and 6 nm (figure2) for the sake of ravaging the glycoproteins on the HIV's membrane [1], because when destroying those proteins the virus loses it's full function (Figure3) .

Principle Function of the Device

We put the coupling gel all over the surface of the table then the patient lay naked on it , where as his body must touch the surface of the table, after starting the device (generating acoustics nano-waves) those waves will spread from the generating medium to the patient's body. Keeping in mind the coupling gel is a medium that helps in spreading the waves from the generators to the human body.

After the spreading of the waves in the patient body and every time it meets with the virus (HIV) it ravages the glycoproteins

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Figure 1. Surface of the Table.

Figure 2. The Frequency Versus Length of the Wave.

Figure 3. A- HIV Active , B- HIV Non-Active.

Figure 4. Proposed Method [6].

(Gp41,Gp120) on the membrane of this dangerous virus (Figure4).

Expected Results

We know that the the glycoproteins (Gp41,Gp120) gives to the HIV it's full function . When we destroy those proteins the virus became non-funcional and the activity of the virus in the human body will be stopped.

Conclusion

This work is just a Theoretical idea we can enter with it to the realistic applications. it's success makes the HIV Virus one of the simplest illnesses and we can cure it easily and the most positive thing in this cure there is no side effects in the human body like the one produced by the pharmaceutical drugs.

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